

ISLAMIC INSURANCE: SIGNIFICANCE, DIFFERENCE, PRINCIPLES AND INSTRUMENTS

Bozorova Shakhnoza Ikromovna

Student of Master's Degree, Foreign Economic Activity,
University of World Economy and Diplomacy

Shaxnoza0102@icloud.com

+998 331567376

Abstract: In this thesis, Islamic insurance – its meaning, difference with conventional insurance, principles and instruments are discussed. Its principles that do not include operations like riba, maysir, gharar are explained. Its main types which are general and family takaful are listed.

Key words: Islamic insurance (Takaful), gharar, riba, maysir, general takaful, family takaful.

Takaful (translated from Arabic - providing mutual guarantees) is an Islamic insurance system based on a profit and loss sharing mechanism between the participants and the takaful operator based on Sharia law. The main objective of Islamic insurance is to protect the interests of its participants from unforeseen adverse events through joint and several participations in the losses of the affected persons, as well as making a profit by insurance participants.

In order to overcome gharar (uncertainty), there must be clarity and full disclosure in the takaful contract. Takaful agreement cannot be concluded, if at least one unknown risk is present.

To eliminate maysir (excitement) in a takaful agreement, the distribution of risks should not contain a speculative element, so the relationship is built on mutual protection (taawun).

For the exclusion of riba (usury), the contribution of the participants is not considered as a premium in traditional insurance, but is regarded as a gift, a donation (tabarru).

Thus, takaful is a system in which policyholders (participants) at the expense of voluntary contributions (tabarru) create a special insurance fund (takaful fund), used to provide mutual financial protection (taawun) when certain adverse unforeseen events occur in their lives.

Thus, takaful has the following distinctive features:

- 1) overcoming the gharar element is achieved due to the fact that the contributions of the participants are considered as donations;
- 2) the fund is formed at the expense of voluntary donations (gift);
- 3) the relations of participants in takaful are based on mutual assistance;
- 4) the participant's contribution is divided into two funds: tabarra and investment fund;
- 5) funds paid to the takaful fund are always returned to the participant;
- 6) the participant receives a stable investment income;
- 7) there are restrictions on the types of takaful products (compliance with Shariah norms);
- 8) investment of a takaful fund can only be carried out in transactions that are not prohibited by Shariah;
- 9) the conditions of inheritance are preserved in accordance with the norms of Shariah;
- 10) the takaful operator only manages the takaful fund;
- 11) the activity of an Islamic insurance company is regulated by a specially created The Shariah Supervisory Board, whose task is to evaluate all the operations of the organization for compliance with the norms of Islamic law.

In the modern world, the main activities of takaful are highlight:¹

- 1) general takaful;
- 2) family takaful.

¹ "Features of the organisation of islamic insurance and prospects of its introduction into the insurance market", ISSN 2073-5537. Вестник-АГТУ.Серия: Экономика 2014. № 1

General takaful covers the area of property insurance, while policyholders can claim a part of the insurer's profit from the funds paid, minus costs.

Within the framework of general takaful, it is customary to distinguish the following types of insurance:

- home insurance (home takaful), which covers the risks of the owner (houseowners takaful) or tenant risk (householders takaful);
- auto takaful (motor takaful), which includes insurance against damage or loss of a vehicle due to fire, theft or accident, as well as compulsory and voluntary motor third party liability insurance for harm to life and health third parties and damage to their property as a result of an accident;
- insurance of property interests against an accident (personal accident takaful).

Family takaful is a personal insurance that differs significantly from the traditional one. It is with this type of insurance that Islamic jurists primarily associate the absence of the element of riba. Profit from investment of insurance reserves life is much lower than 100%, which, according to most Islamic jurists, fits well into the established norms of Shariah. Thus, endowment life insurance in such form is quite acceptable for Muslims.

Within the framework of family takaful, the following insurance products are distinguished:²

- family takaful;
- investment takaful (cumulative life insurance - investment linked takaful);
- takaful for education (child education takaful);
- medical & health takaful;
- medical takaful for persons traveling abroad;
- takaful against accidents.

Sources:

² “Features of the organisation of islamic insurance and prospects of its introduction into the insurance market”, ISSN 2073-5537. Вестник-АГТУ.Серия: Экономика 2014. № 1

1. "Islamic insurance (Takaful)" (R.I.Bekkin, 2012) – 140 p.
<https://kpfu.ru/portal/docs/F880698254/1.pdf>
2. "Islamic takaful insurance: Jurisprudents to Applications", Ahmed M. Sabbagh .– Amman : Author , 346 p. 2012.
3. "Takaful insurance report", 2022.
<https://www.centralbank.ae/media/5pfeshog/takaful-insurance-report-2022-1.pdf>
4. "Islamic Jurisprudence and its Proofs", p-4/442, Dr. Wahbi Al-Zuhaili.
5. "Islamic Insurance Between Theory and Practice ar., Abdel Sami' Al-Masri/72
6. Insurance in Islamic Sharia and law. Dr. Ghareeb Al Jammal, Al Shoruk publishing house in Jeddah.
7. "Features of the organisation of islamic insurance and prospects of its introduction into the insurance market", ISSN 2073-5537. Вестник-АГТУ.Серия: Экономика 2014. № 1